

Molten silicon at the heart of a novel energy storage system

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Abstract

AMADEUS (www.amadeus-project.eu) is a FET-OPEN project funded by the European Commission to research a new generation of materials and solid state devices for ultra-high temperature energy storage and conversion. By exploring silicon-based alloys as new phase change materials (PCMs), latent heat in the range of 1000-2000 kWh/m³ is achievable; which means an order of magnitude greater than that of typical salt-based PCMs used in concentrated solar power (CSP). In addition, silicon-based PCMs lead to storage temperatures well beyond 1000 °C, and so this project aims at breaking the mark of ~ 600 °C rarely exceeded by current state of the art thermal energy storage (TES). This paper describes the project R&D activities and first results, and comments on challenges towards new systems combining latent heat energy storage in molten silicon and hybrid thermionic-photovoltaic (TIPV) heat-to-power conversion. Also, numerical steady-state and transient simulations of a lab-scale TES prototype are presented; where silicon phase-change, heat loss mechanisms and heat-to-power conversion analyses are conducted. For real cases studied, percentage of energy stored available for conversion strongly depends on the scale, design and materials; with conversions above 75-85% considered feasible for medium-large scale applications.

Introduction

Greater penetration of renewable energy sources is necessary to address some of the major challenges that the present world economy faces: energy security, pollution, sustainability and climate change [1]. Reaching the climate goals of the Paris agreement (2015) will require increasing quantities of renewable energy to be generated in the urban environment and the availability of energy storage technologies at competitive cost structures. The latter is essential in order to manage a future electric system based on renewables.

In this paper we present a novel latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) system that has the potential to achieve one of the highest energy densities among existing energy storage solutions. The proposed LHTES [2,3] considers silicon-based alloys as new phase change materials (PCMs) combined with novel solid-state heat to power conversion technologies able to operate at temperatures above 1000 °C, in particular hybrid thermionic-photovoltaic (TIPV) devices. Silicon-based alloys latent heat falls within the range of 1000-2000 kWh/m³ and melting points far above 1000 °C. In Figure 1 the latent heat of fusion of different materials as a function of the melting temperature is shown. This figure illustrates the potential of silicon (1230 kWh/m³) and boron (2680 kWh/m³) compared with latent heats of typical salts used in CSP, such as NaNO₃ (110 kWh/m³) and KNO₃ (156 kWh/m³). Figure 1 also shows that silicon and boron PCMs provide higher storage energy densities than most forms of energy storage, including electrochemical batteries and pressurized hydrogen.

Figure 1: Latent heat of fusion of different materials as a function of the melting temperature.

The main challenge of the proposed LHTES solution is the very high operating temperature, especially concerning the heat-to-power conversion system. Nonetheless, solid state converters, such as thermionics [4], thermophotovoltaics (TPV) [5,6] and hybrid thermionic-photovoltaics [7], are perfectly suited for such high temperatures, mainly because they are based on the direct emission of electrons and photons through space (non-direct contact), eliminating the need for a working fluid and moving parts. These converters also benefit from extremely high power densities (power-to-weight and power-to-volume ratio), low maintenance costs due to the absence of moving parts, and silent operation. The latter is relevant for energy storage applications in an urban environment. Figure 2 presents a sketch of the LHTES concept under development in the AMADEUS project. It can be observed how part of the energy storage will be converted into electricity by a hybrid TIPV device, while the remainder is delivered in the form of heat (e.g. it could be used for hot water and/or heating appliances).

Figure 2: Sketch of the AMADEUS LHTES concept.

AMADEUS project

AMADEUS is a FET-OPEN research project funded by the European Commission for the development of a new generation of ultra-compact energy storage devices based on

molten silicon and solid state heat-to-power converters [8]. The AMADEUS project is coordinated by the IES-UPM and, including the coordinator has the participation of seven European partners with experience in the fields of high temperature materials (NTNU and FRI), fluid-dynamics and finite elements analysis (CERTH), thermal insulation (USTUTT), and solid state heat-to-power conversion based on thermionics (CNR and Ionvac) and photovoltaics (IES-UPM) [8].

Started in January 2017, the AMADEUS project has a budget of ~ 3.3 M€ (3 years) and the final aim is to demonstrate the proof-of-concept of a new LHTES concept based on ultra-high temperature PCMs and solid state heat-to-power converters. In order to reach the final goal of the project, a number of materials and technologies have been investigated, and two proofs of concept are scheduled:

- novel PCMs based on the silicon-boron system with ultra-high melting point and latent heat,
- novel refractory lining composites based on carbides, nitrides and oxides for the PCM container walls,
- advanced thermally insulated PCM casing enabling small heat losses,
- proof of concept of a novel hybrid thermionic-photovoltaic (TIPV) device [7],
- proof of concept of the final complete LHTES device comprising the elements described above.

The project is subdivided into two main blocks: developing a high temperature heat storage unit, and developing a high temperature energy conversion module. The first block comprises the study of silicon-boron PCMs, PCM-container interaction, heat transfer analysis in the PCM and thermal insulation. The second block of the project studies the high temperature operation of TIPV converters. All of the advances performed over the first years of the project will serve as a basis for the design and construction of a LHTES prototype during the last year of the project, which will allow demonstration of a proof of concept for the complete system.

As mentioned above, silicon-boron PCMs are a smart choice as this binary alloys allow very high energy storage densities. The selection of proper Si-B alloys and the alloys container material at elevate temperatures is studied through experimental and theoretical (FactSage software) thermodynamic work at NTNU [9]. First conclusions indicate that the alloys closer to the eutectic point in the Si-B system (i.e. ~3% in weight of B) are the best candidates as they have a larger enthalpy of fusion at solidus and a slightly lower melting point (~1385 °C) [10], additionally, boron is significantly more expensive than silicon, so a small addition is more feasible. These binary alloys also present the advantage of a decrease of volumetric change during liquid-solid states transitions. Other kinds of binary and ternary alloys including Si, B, Cu, and Fe (among others) are currently under investigation in the AMADEUS project by NTNU and FRI. One of the main challenges faced in this project is to develop standard procedures and instrumentation for examining thermo-physical properties of silicon and silicon-boron alloys in semi-liquid and liquid states.

PCM-container interaction is also being investigated at FRI and NTNU [9]. Both silicon and boron are active elements and they are susceptible to oxidation, nitridization and carburization in contact with O, N, and C, which are typical constituents of high temperature refractory materials (e.g. C, SiC, Si₃N₄, BN, etc.). The behavior these refractories in contact liquid Si-B alloys is being investigated within the project [10].

During the first year, both C and BN have been identified as interesting candidates. The main difference is that graphite is wetted by liquid silicon, while boron nitride is not. It has also been found that alloying silicon with boron results in a decrease the wetting of boron nitride (BN) containers [11]. More details of this particular research, conducted between FRI and NTNU, can be found in [12].

Analysis of the complex heat transfer mechanisms occurring inside the proposed PCM is being developed on the basis of the ANSYS® Fluent platform by CERTH [13]. This model will allow the study of the PCM solidification/melting process, with incorporation of the parametric study on the heat loss variation under different emitter surfaces and container volumes. The final aim is the thorough investigation of the stress-strain between the PCM and its container. Regarding heat transfer analysis of the overall system, a CFD model has been developed in COMSOL® [14]. This model incorporates all relevant properties of a number of suitable thermal insulation materials which can stand temperatures up to 2000 °C. Initially, a multi-layer thermal insulation is being considered, aiming at defining an overall insulation which accomplishes a compromise solution between minimum single-layers thickness and low-cost [13].

Finally, energy conversion block activities are devoted to the proof of concept of the novel thermionic-photovoltaic (TIPV) device [7]. While both technologies (thermionic -TI- and thermophotovoltaic -TPV-) have been demonstrated separately by researchers participating in this project [15,16], the hybrid TIPV device has only been considered theoretically [7]. The TIPV device (Figure 3) consist of a tandem arrangement between a thermionic and a photovoltaic cell, comprising two main elements: the TIPV cathode (or emitter) and the TIPV anode. The TIPV cathode is the radiating element; it irradiates electrons and photons when heated due to a low work function and high optical emissivity. The TIPV anode comprises the thermionic collector and the TPV cell; the former will absorb the electrons (since its work function is even lower than that of the emitter) and the TPV cell will absorb the emitted photons, generating an electron-hole pair. Electrons collected in the thermionic collector recombine with holes photo-generated in the TPV cell; thus closing the circuit and series connecting the thermionic and photovoltaic sub-devices. Finally, the emitter and the TPV cell anode are externally connected to deliver external electrical power. The combination of both devices is expected to provide a significant increment of the power density compared with the independent thermionic and photovoltaic devices.

Figure 3: The thermionic-photovoltaic (TIPV) device [7].

TIPV converter has the potential of achieving efficiencies of ~ 40% [7]. Furthermore, a TIPV generator illuminated by a 1400 °C radiant source may produce more than 100 kW/m² of electricity, which is about 500 times the power density of conventional flat plate PV systems (~200 W/m²). In regards to the challenges faced in this block of activities, the main ones are the need of a vacuum atmosphere and micro-spacers (for the separation between the TIPV anode and cathode) that are indispensable conditions for the successful operation of the TI device.

Applications

Thermal energy storage for power generation is almost exclusively used in concentrated solar power (CSP) systems, where the sun's energy is stored in the form of sensible heat in molten salts and converted upon demand into electricity using a conventional Rankine engine. The combination of (low energetically dense) molten salts and Rankine engines has resulted in the construction of very large CSP power plants of typically 100's of MWs that are placed in distant locations; thus requiring complex civil engineering, new wiring and grid adaptation. The construction of smaller (kW-class) CSP systems is interesting in order to bring modularity to this technology. The remarkably high energy density of molten silicon (~1200 kWh/m³) and the very high power density of solid state converters such as TIPV (~100 kW/m²) will bring a new paradigm to the CSP sector, enabling extremely compact designs that could be used in smaller and simpler configurations, even integrated in urban areas.

The ultra-high energy density of molten silicon also opens the door to a new kind of application for thermal energy storage, which is the direct storage of electricity using an electric furnace for melting. Although thermodynamically counterintuitive, the extremely low prices of the electricity produced by renewable sources, such as wind and solar, are suggesting that using electricity for heating will become more economical than burning fuels. In this scenario, the proposed LHTES system could be used for electricity storage and co- or tri-generation in domestic applications (electricity/heating and electricity/heating/cooling). Besides, many other niche applications may appear in the future, including waste heat storage and recovery in industrial processes, space power storage and conversion, etc.

In principle, the proposed LHTES device could cover from a few kilowatts-hour (kWh) of capacity for domestic applications to some megawatts-hours (MWh) in the case of large accumulators. However, optimum sizing of the system is a key design aspect that is being carefully investigated, and must take into account the specific application requirements and the system performance (mostly heat transfer and thermal insulation requirements). It is worth mentioning that despite focusing on the potential of a lab-scale (very small) LHTES prototype, aimed at proof of concept of the proposed solution, scaling up a LHTES will lead to higher storage efficiencies (lower heat losses) and subsequently, higher full-cycle efficiencies and performance ratios per unit of storage capacity. Nevertheless, we will also give some insight on this in the following section.

Lab-scale prototype

The final goal of the AMADEUS project is to realize, first, a proof of concept of the TIPV device, and then a proof of concept of the full LHTES device. The later activity will start in the third year of the project, when all the other elements have been properly defined. However, the activities concerning the design, materials selection and sizing of the LHTES prototype have already started. In this section we present the CFD modelling

developed for the LHTES prototype, which accounts for all material properties, realistic boundary conditions, and the silicon-based alloy phase change. Once developed, this model allows both steady-state and transient simulations in order to reproduce in a quite realistic manner the charge-discharge of the system during real operation, by means of heat transfer and structural mechanic calculations.

System Model

In order to select the final prototype design a number of possible configurations for the AMADEUS Project prototype have been modelled and analyzed; aiming for the best compromise in performance and simplicity at lab-scale. We have addressed the problem definition (materials selection, thermal and mechanical analysis), followed by a CFD analysis in both steady-state and transient scenarios. Finally, on the basis of modelling results, analysis and discussion, a final prototype design has been proposed, that aims to maximize a merit function defined as the quotient between the radiated power towards the TIPV converter and the overall heat losses (P_{rad}/P_{tot}). Accordingly, in chronological order the following parameters have been improved/defined: heat losses through the outer walls, crucible geometry and crucible holder shape, insulation layer thickness and disposition, materials and overall sizing. In this model, only photon radiation is considered for simplicity; thus disregarding the electron emission from the TIPV cathode/emitter.

The design proposed for the LHTES prototype is sketched in Figure 4; where the different elements and materials are indicated. The overall dimensions of the prototype are 40 cm diameter and 37 cm high; the volume of silicon-alloy contained in the crucible is 0.5 L (~ 1.16 Kg Si). The external casing of the prototype is made of stainless steel. Graphite fiber board (RFA), fumed silica board (WDS Ultra) and graphite fiber mat (GFA) are considered as possible insulation materials. The crucible holder is made of a rigid graphite fiber board (MFA), and the crucible could be made of a graphite composite or a high density graphite. Results presented below consider a graphite composite crucible. For the heat input during the charging stage of the prototype a graphite resistance heater was selected.

Figure 4: Proposed design and materials for the LHTES prototype.

The TIPV device (which will be water cooled) is not included in Figure 4, however its presence and performance is simulated by means of the boundary conditions defined at the bottom surface of the crucible and inner surface of the cylindrical GFA insulation

layers. In the real prototype the TIPV converter (anode) will be placed underneath the bottom of the crucible; the bottom surface of the crucible will act as the cathode (emitter). Finally, the inner cavity of the prototype will be filled with argon gas at atmospheric pressure; while the TIPV device would be kept in a vacuum atmosphere by means of an infrared radiation-transparent quartz chamber precisely occupying the vacant volume beneath the crucible in Figure 4.

Relevant properties for the simulations conducted with all of the selected materials are presented in Table 1; except for the thermo-chemical properties of the Si-alloy that are presented in Table 2. Single values indicated in Tables 1 and 2 correspond to the particular value of each property at the referred conditions; however, properties are defined as a function of the temperature in the model developed. The silicon phase-change is simulated considering its latent heat of fusion; adding this magnitude at the phase-change temperature to the silicon heat capacity. In addition, at the melting point (T_m) of the pure silicon, its properties are simulated with a sharp phase transition (within a few degrees Celsius); being the properties for $T < T_m$ and $T > T_m$ those corresponding to the solid state and liquid state, respectively.

Table 1: Properties of the LHTES prototype involved materials.

Material	Thermal conductivity, k [W/(K·m)]		Max. operation temperature [°C]	Thermal expansion, α [m/K]
	T = 25 °C	T > 1000 °C		
WDS_Ultra	0.034	-	1000	-
RFA	-	0.3	2000	-
GFA	-	0.5	2200	-
MFA	-	0.3	2000	-
Graphite composite	1.7	3.2	> 2500	3.5×10^{-6}
High density graphite	140	70	> 2500	4.8×10^{-6}
Stainless steel	240	-	940	2.4×10^{-5}
Argon (gas)	0.02	0.05	-	-

Table 2: Thermo-physical properties of pure silicon ($T_m=1414^\circ\text{C}$), which is selected as the PCM for this model.

Property	Temperature [°C]		Phase change ($T = T_m$)
	T < T_m	T > T_m	
Density, ρ [kg/m ³]	2535	2520	-
Thermal conductivity, k [W/(K·m)]	25	50	-
Heat capacity, C_p [J/(kg·K)]	1040	1040	-
Dynamic viscosity, μ [kg/(m·s)]	-	0.06	-
Latent heat, L [J/kg]	-	-	1.8×10^6
Thermal expansion coef., α [m/K]	2.6×10^{-6}	-	-
Emissivity, ε [-]	0.7	0.2	-

Now, in Figure 5 (left) the boundary conditions (BCs) and the heat transfer mechanisms for the thermal modelling are indicated. Conduction heat transfer phenomena occurs in all materials/elements; and the thermal conductivity as function of the temperature ($k(T)$) for each element/material is considered for conductive heat transfer. Convective heat losses are defined at the outer walls and at the inner surface of the GFA insulation; the convective heat transfer coefficients (h) are $20 \text{ W}/(\text{K}\cdot\text{m}^2)$ and $5 \text{ W}/(\text{K}\cdot\text{m}^2)$, respectively. Radiation occurs at the heater surface ($\varepsilon = 0.9$), at the top surface of the Si-alloy ($\varepsilon = 0.7$ -

0.2), at the bottom surface of the crucible ($\epsilon = 0.3$) and at the inner surface of the GFA insulation ($\epsilon = 0.9$). The emissivity considered at the bottom surface of the crucible of 0.3 does not correspond to that of the crucible material but to a rough estimation of the so called effective emissivity; which is the emissivity resultant from the net radiative balance between the emitter (attached to the bottom of the crucible) and the TIPV anode. Eventual modifications of the emitter (e.g. selective coatings) will change the effective emissivity and will dramatically impact the heat transfer within the PCM. Thus, a more thorough analysis of the radiative exchange in the actual emitter surface is required to accurately determine the effective emissivity. This will be done in future work.

In Figure 5 (right), BCs for the structural mechanical modelling are presented. It can be observed that the insulation elements effect are disregarded (those are considered flexible) and that the remaining surfaces BCs are divided between free displacement and fixed boundaries.

Figure 5: Boundary conditions and heat transfer mechanisms for the thermal calculations in the model (left), and BCs for the structural analysis modelling. Axi-symmetric view of the prototype.

Steady-state analysis

The model of the LHTES prototype is used for thermal and structural mechanic calculation at steady-state. The most demanding operating conditions (higher temperatures and temperature gradients) of the prototype occur when its charging stage finishes and right before the discharge stage initiates, i.e. the bottom part of the PCM is slightly beyond 1414 °C, the silicon's melting point. Thus, this time is the one analysed below.

In Figure 6 (left), the temperature distribution of the LHTES prototype is presented. The highest temperatures are at the heating element (1567 °C) and top surface of the silicon-alloy (1511 °C), and the temperature of the radiant surface towards the TIPV device (crucible bottom surface) is about 1103 °C, which implies a temperature gradient of 97 °C in the bottom crucible wall (not considering convective flow of the liquid). The temperature at the outer walls is below 35 °C, which is a reasonable temperature since the real prototype wall will be water-cooled; and it has also been assured that no material reaches its maximum operation temperature.

In Figure 6 (right), results of the thermal and structural mechanics analysis combined are presented. The von Mises stress criteria is used to evaluate whether the different materials will yield when subjected to the strains associated with thermal expansion [17]. The von Mises stress is compared to the material's yield stress (or to the ultimate tensile stress when it is lower than the former), to determine whether any material would yield or fracture. The maximum displacement due to deformation is also obtained from these calculations. In all cases, strain suffered by the materials are below their limits (as well as under their maximum operation temperature); the most critical conditions occur at the crucible holder, followed by the interfaces at the crucible holder-crucible, crucible holder-wall and alloy surface-crucible. At these points surface coatings and clearances, facilitating free displacement parallel to the corresponding interfaces, will reduce mechanical stress due to thermal expansion.

Figure 6: Temperature distribution (left) and Von Mises (structural mechanics analysis) when the system is completely charged (all Si-alloy melted).

As mentioned above, this design was optimized aiming to maximize the merit function $P_{\text{rad}}/P_{\text{tot}}$ (expressed in percentage); which is obtained to be 62.9%. This means that 62.9% of the storage energy is available for the subsequent conversion by means of the TIPV device. It is worth mentioning that scaling up the system will result in significantly lower heat losses through the outer wall, due to the lower surface-to-volume ratio. For a real LHTES, $P_{\text{rad}}/P_{\text{tot}}$ ratios above 75-85% are considered feasible (and above 90% desirable) when scaling up the system and optimising its design at the same time.

Other factors, besides the scale of the LHTES unit, will also affect the merit function $P_{\text{rad}}/P_{\text{tot}}$. A slight variation in the materials properties of the crucible (in particular thermal conductivity), is translated to a relevant decrease/increase of the merit function. E.g. varying the thermal conductivity from 2 to 70 W/(K·m) leads to an increase of $P_{\text{rad}}/P_{\text{tot}}$ ratio from 62.9% to 78.4%; since the increase of P_{rad} is greater than that of P_{tot} . This effect is damped with the scale, but it will never be negligible. It is worth noticing here, that very low thermal conductivities of the crucible are not desired since this will be translated to a lower temperature of the emitter (due to higher temperature gradient at the base of the crucible).

Dynamic analysis

Transient simulations of the discharge of the LHTES prototype were also conducted. The interest is in analysing the temperature distribution, the length of the discharge periods and the rate of power generated.

In Figure 7, the temperature distribution along the vertical axis in the Si-alloy and crucible during discharge is presented; discharge takes 80 minutes. The silicon bottom (crucible bottom) temperature goes from 1414 to 1337 °C (1103 to 1072 °C), and according to an in-house (idealized) TPV model based on InGaAsSb semiconductor devices (bandgap of 0.51 eV), this is translated to a power generation per unit area in the range 3.85-2.94 W/cm² [18]. It must be noticed the important drawback of the large temperature gradient in the crucible. If TPV cells were operated at 1414°C (temperature at point A in the inset of Figure 7), the power generation density (watts per unit of device area) would be as high as 11.4 W/cm² [18]. Besides, this power could be doubled by using TIPV instead of TPV up to ~20 W/cm² (1000 times greater than conventional solar PV cells) [7].

The expected output electric power, temperature at emitter and TIPV device, and discharge times will be strongly affected by the effective emissivity. Thus, it is only possible to predict with the generated power density with reasonable accuracy. Furthermore, the electrical energy that can be removed will also vary significantly if a rear reflector is placed in the cells, thus return heat to the emitter. The latter will increase the efficiency, although it will not change the density of electrical power; that is, it will take longer to solidify since the power density of the TIPV conversion remains constant for a given emitter temperature.

Figure 7: Temperature distribution along vertical axis in the crucible during discharge (time step: 120 sec).

In Figure 8 (left), convective and radiative heat losses are shown. Radiation towards the TIPV device (P_{rad}), convective losses to the ambient (P_{conv}), and convective (P_{conv_cav}) and radiative (P_{rad_cav}) losses through the cavity for the TIPV devices are presented separately. Ideally, we would like to minimise all heat losses with the exception of P_{rad} ; thus maximising the P_{rad}/P_{tot} ratio. In Figure 8 (right), radiated power (from the emitter) over total power losses (P_{rad}/P_{tot}) during the discharge time is presented. It can be observed that P_{rad}/P_{tot} ratio decreases from 62.9 to 60.0% during discharge (61.5% average) due to the temperature drop at the emitter surface. These values are acceptable for the initial lab-scale system prototype, where system size must be kept at a minimum to facilitate

experimentation and reduce fabrication costs. Larger $P_{\text{rad}}/P_{\text{tot}}$ ratios will be attained by scaling up the system and optimizing the design to larger sizes. Indeed, this analysis will allow the determination of the minimum system size in future works.

Figure 8: Convection and radiation heat losses (left) and radiated power (from the emitter) over total power losses, $P_{\text{rad}}/P_{\text{tot}}$ ratio (right), during the discharge time.

Conclusions

In this paper we have described a new energy storage system based on molten silicon and solid state energy conversion devices. This system is the target of a FET-OPEN European funded Project named AMADEUS (www.amadeus-project.eu) that started in January 2017 and will finish in December 2019. The main advantage of the concept relies on the extremely high latent heat of silicon and silicon alloys ($\sim 1200 \text{ kWh/m}^3$) that clearly surpass most forms of energy storage, including batteries ($< 500 \text{ kWh/m}^3$) and molten salts ($< 100 \text{ kWh/m}^3$). Examples of possible applications range from a few kilowatt-hour (kWh) of capacity to some megawatt-hours (MWh), in the case of large accumulators. Specifically, the proposed system could be used for electricity storage (using electric furnaces) for co- or tri-generation in domestic applications, direct solar energy storage (CSP), and energy storage at industrial waste heat recovery systems, among many others.

A small lab-scale prototype, which will eventually be fabricated within the AMADEUS project, is analysed in this paper. This prototype is a proof of concept, it is not optimized in terms of energy storage efficiency, but in terms of flexible experimentation. This lab-prototype contains 0.5 litres of silicon, representing a latent heat storage capacity of $\sim 615 \text{ Wh}_{\text{th}}$. According to CFD simulations, solidification of silicon will last about 80 min, during which $\sim 63 \%$ of the latent heat will be delivered as radiation towards the solid state energy converter, which will convert part of this radiation into electricity. Assuming a conversion efficiency of 40%, it means that 25% of the stored latent heat will be retrieved as electricity. This relatively low conversion efficiency is mostly attributed to the small dimensions of the lab-scale prototype, characterized by a large surface-to-volume ratio that results in relatively large losses through the thermal insulation. Scaling up the system is expected to produce conversion efficiencies in the range of 30-40%; thus, future work will focus on determining the minimum size of the system that will enable the profitability of the system in different applications.

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